

Analyzing the Spatial Distribution of Fuel Stations in Harare, Zimbabwe: Leveraging OpenStreetMap for Disaster Preparedness, Mitigation and Recovery

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Natural or man-made disasters pose serious risks to communities all over the world and frequently have dire repercussions, including the loss of life, destruction of property, and disruption of social order [1]. Fire occurrences are particularly dangerous among these calamities, especially when they include infrastructure such as gasoline stations [2]. The potential for large-scale fire catastrophes underscores the need to ensure the safety of gasoline station infrastructure, as evidenced by occurrences documented in Zimbabwe [3]. Petroleum derivatives, such as gasoline, diesel, kerosene, and liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), have the potential to ignite fires when handled improperly [4]. It is clear that a comprehensive fire danger assessment is necessary, which highlights the need for proactive fire management planning [4]. Between 1993 and 2004, there were around 243 fire-related incidents at fuel service stations worldwide that were recorded [5]. It is evident that these sites present significant risks.

Geospatial technology has become an invaluable instrument for disaster preparedness, response, and mitigation as a result of these issues [6]. By offering open data necessary for disaster response and mitigation, initiatives such as the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team (HOT) and the utilization of platforms similar to OpenStreetMap (OSM) have made substantial progress in these efforts [7]. These systems ensure the availability of high-quality data for efficient mitigation measures and provide quick and open access to geospatial data, facilitating prompt disaster response activities [8]. The OSM data consists of many datasets that use points, lines, polygons, and area attributes to represent real-world features [9,10]. These databases include characteristics that are useful for study, mitigation, recovery, and preparedness for disasters.

Through querying the OSM database using the QuickOSM plugin [11] on the Quantum Geographic Information System (QGIS) [12], there were only 54 petrol stations in Harare

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listed in the OSM database. After identifying this gap, petrol station addresses were collected from the Zimbabwe Petroleum Regulatory Authority (ZPRA). This revealed that there are actually 324 petrol stations in Harare, meaning 288 petrol stations are missing from the OSM database. Using GIS techniques and the Java OpenStreetMap Editor (JOSM) [13] and EveryDoor [14] open-source mobile application, the remaining 288 petrol stations were mapped into the OSM database.

This research aimed to address the challenges posed by fire hazards, particularly in petrol station infrastructure, through the application of GIS techniques. The study conducted geoprocessing analyses, including overlay and proximity analysis, using building footprints, conventional construction standards for the siting of petroleum liquid and gas facilities, and public spaces such as markets, parks, schools, hospitals, places of worship, and road networks in Harare, Zimbabwe. Also, nearest neighbor analysis and Euclidean distance analysis [15] were performed using petrol station points to identify danger zones and potential vulnerabilities. The study also sought to map petrol stations, obtain their exact locations, and extract pertinent data from OSM and other sources using GIS methodologies. The study also aims to categorize areas at risk of fire hazards based on various factors, such as proximity to fuel stations and the location of filling stations according to Zimbabwean government regulations and retail premises, as well as other factors identified through spatial analysis.

Furthermore, it sought to offer practical suggestions and solutions for improving public safety and lessening the effects of fire disasters in Harare, Zimbabwe, offering insightful information for initiatives related to disaster preparation, mitigation, and recovery to advance resilience and sustainable development in the country while also adding to the scientific understanding of the dangers of fire hazards related to gasoline stations as well as providing a replicable approach to mapping external data into the OSM database.

This study's methodology combines spatial analytic methodologies and data extraction from GIS analysis. To fully comprehend the gaps that now exist, the research first starts by gaining access to the data that is already available on the OSM Database. The gasoline stations missing in the OSM database were then mapped into the database, where pertinent data such as locations and infrastructure aspects were recorded. Then relevant data was extracted from OSM. The procedure involved extracting comprehensive information on the locations of buildings, roads, and public spaces, including playgrounds, marketplaces, hospitals, and schools, from the massive OSM database. This extraction was done using the QuickOSM plugin on QGIS software, which shows the richness of the OSM database and the procedures used in this study are provided and detailed in the methodology section. All geospatial datasets, including those from OSM and the Zimbabwe Petroleum Regulatory Authority (ZPRA), are attached and accessible for replication of the analysis.

A thorough examination of the geographic distribution of filling stations, public buildings, and fire service stations was done using the GIS technique. The objective of this research was to categorize areas at risk of fire hazards according to the Zimbabwean government's standards for the placement of retail and LPG filling stations. These rules include factors such as the distance from fuel stations and other infrastructural concerns. To fully comprehend the spatial distribution of fuel stations in relation to fire stations, residential buildings, and public amenities like schools, hospitals, places of worship, markets, parks, and more, techniques like Euclidean, nearest neighborhood analysis, and

geoprocessing analysis were used. The mapping results are presented as maps, graphs and tables, where the identified risk zones are visualized, and detailed analysis is provided.

To perform the analysis, the number of buildings in each of the four fire danger risk zones—very high, high, medium, and low risk—was grouped and examined. In order to determine the number of structures in each of these designated zones, a query to the OSM dataset was made. This yields important information on the possible effects of fire hazard events on different regions within the research area.

This study aimed to provide crucial information for risk and disaster management (preparedness, mitigation, and recovery) by conducting a thorough investigation of fire hazard threats associated with petrol stations in Harare, Zimbabwe. Utilizing GIS techniques and geospatial data from OSM, the project sought to improve public safety, mitigate the effects of fire disasters, and advance the scientific understanding of fire hazard risks. The methodology, which included collaboration with government agencies, ensured that essential data, such as petrol station addresses and coordinates provided by the Zimbabwe Petroleum Regulatory Authority (ZPRA), were accurately uploaded and integrated into the OSM database. This was achieved using the JOSM, with validation through the EveryDoor mobile application, ensuring data alignment with OSM's structure and protocols.

The study identified significant data gaps within OSM, particularly the absence of many petrol stations in Harare, which were addressed by integrating the ZPRA datasets. While OSM proved to be a valuable source of geospatial data, the study highlights the need for continuous updates and systematic data validation to enhance its utility. Recommendations include encouraging policymakers to leverage OSM for disaster risk reduction strategies and fostering collaborations between government agencies and the OSM community to ensure data accuracy and relevance.

The findings and recommendations of this study emphasize the importance of integrating external datasets with open-source geospatial databases to improve hazard mapping and risk management efforts. By doing so, it is possible to enhance public safety and disaster preparedness, making OSM a more reliable tool for both local and global disaster response initiatives.

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